

The Cotoname language – the primary sources
Arranged by Haukur Þorgeirsson¹ and Alaric Hall²

Cotoname is an extinct language once spoken near Camargo by the Rio Grande. Two vocabularies gathered in the 19th century are the only known documentation of the language. The first was collected by Jean Louis Berlandier and/or Rafael Chowell in 1828–1829 or so. The second was collected by Albert S. Gatschet in December 1886. The purpose of this publication is to make these two primary sources available.

As Dylan Ruediger and Ruby MacDougall (2023) have recently emphasised, the humanities have been slow to join the growing ‘open data’ movement. Nevertheless, making research data accessible enables the verification and further development of research, which can benefit the humanities as it has other fields. In that spirit, this publication embraces open-data approaches by making available data gathered in the course of Haukur Þorgeirsson’s research on Cotoname.

Our work adheres to a ‘good enough’ approach to data-publication. While the transcriptions published here are intended to meet the high standards of accuracy customary in philological editing, the digital manuscript facsimiles included are not of archive quality. Nonetheless, we see these images as serviceable and have taken the view that future researchers would prefer to have access to them than not.

This work is published concurrently to the article “The Cotoname language – an analysis”, to appear in the *International Journal of American Linguistics*. Here we give only the minimal background information needed to make sense of the primary sources, with much more analytical material in the other article.

The following material is included here in this order.

- a) A new alphabetically arranged vocabulary of Cotoname forms based on both primary sources.
- b) A transcript of the six pages containing Cotoname information in Berlandier’s linguistic manuscript. The transcript contains the column of French words and the column of Cotoname words, labelled Carisso de Camargo. The column marked “en Mulato” contains Comecrudo words which are not transcribed here.
- c) Photographs of the same six pages of Berlandier’s manuscript, British Library add. ms. 38720, taken by Haukur Þorgeirsson at the British Library on April 29, 2024. The manuscript is challenging to photograph, it is quite tightly bound and the inner margin is small. The resulting photographs are aesthetically imperfect but every word and letter can be read.
- d) Photographs of Albert S. Gatschet’s field notes on Cotoname in NAA MS 297-a taken by Alaric Hall at the National Anthropological Archives on November 14, 2017. The Cotoname notes are on pages 40–41, 54–57 and 62.

¹ The Árni Magnússon Institute.

² University of Leeds.

- e) Photographs of Albert S. Gatschet's organized Cotoname vocabulary in NAA MS 297-b based on his own field notes. Photographs taken by Alaric Hall at the National Anthropological Archives on November 14, 2017. The Cotoname vocabulary is on pages 184–190.

Gatschet's data was previously published by Swanton (1940). The Berlandier data has not been previously published but some glimpses were made available by Goddard (1979). A selection of other publications which include some analysis of Cotoname or useful background information is found in the bibliography.

Cotoname vocabulary – an introduction

The following is an alphabetical list of Cotoname forms with English translations. The vocabulary is based on the two preserved sources. One is a linguistic manuscript compiled by Jean Louis Berlandier and Rafael Chowell in 1828–1829 or so. This source is referred to as (B) in the vocabulary. The orthography used in these forms is based on the phonetic value of letters in French and, in the case of 'j', in Spanish.

The other source consists of the field notes of Albert S. Gatschet from his visit to Las Prietas in December 1886. Gatschet's two informants were Miterio and Santos Cavázos. They are referred to with (M) and (S) in the list. Gatschet made use of an early Americanist phonetic notation. He frequently uses the symbol 'χ', indicating a velar fricative, which we have here alphabetized as if it were 'h'.

In the vocabulary below, we have corrected simple misspellings, added missing accents, and removed redundant accents in the French and Spanish forms, using e.g. *prêtre* for *pretre*, *correr* for *corrér* and *belduque* for *velduque*. Where Gatschet's manuscript has non-standard forms which are ambiguous or may reflect local usage, we have left them in the text.

How to read an entry

The following entry can serve as an example:

yómo – horn, male; *horn (los cuernos); macho S (54, 40)*

First the Cotoname form is given in bold, **yómo**, then the sense is given in English. This word has two known meanings, "horn" and "male". This is followed by a quotation of the original source in italics. Here there are two quotations, separated by a semi-colon. First there is *horn (los cuernos)* which is on page 54 in Gatschet's notebook and mixes English and Spanish as Gatschet sometimes does. The second citation, *macho*, is to page 40 of the notebook. The letter S stands for Santos Cavázos, the source of our information for this word.

When chaotic field notes are worked into a tidy vocabulary, some contextual information is inevitably lost along the way. Readers are encouraged to follow up the citations and consult the primary sources for themselves. This is particularly

important for the words for the cardinal directions on pages 54 and 57 where there was apparently some misunderstanding which has been corrected in a way that is not completely clear.

The spelling of the Cotoname forms is left as it is in the original manuscripts except that the use of capital letters is normalized. Cross-references between forms which are likely to be related are intended to help the reader navigate the variety in orthographic representation.

Cotoname vocabulary

- aaqouâ** – thunder; *tonnerre* B (24v)
aau – sun; *soleil* B (24v) – see also **ó, ó; ò**
a-eihe-manao – thumb; *le pouce* B (25v)
á'h – water; *agua* M (40) – see also **aje**
áχ, áχ' – water; *agua* S (40) – see also **aje**
áχ katám – river, Rio Grande; *río, Río Grande* S (41)
aia-ia – foot; *le pied* B (24v)
aiam-na – womb; *la matrice* B (24v)
aime-a-cou – knee; *le genou* B (24v)
aim-jajan – married man; *homme marié* B (24v)
ajuahué – sea; *la mer* B (25v)
aja – day; *le jour* B (26r)
aje – water; *agua* B (25r) – see also **á'h** and **áχ**
aje-a – mouth; *bouche, sans la langue* B (25r)
aje-an – river, *une rivière* B (25v)
Ajebaham – Rio Grande; *Rio grande* B (25v)
ajehouaan (*prononcé du nez*) – god; *dieu* B (25v)
aje-ouēma – upper teeth; *dents supérieures* B (25r)
aje-ouetehen – lower teeth; *dents inférieures* B (25r)
aje-oura – arm; *bras* B (25r)
ajouan – ribs; *côtes* B (25r)
akwanámie – he is chewing; *está masticando* S (56)
ám – fish; *poisson* B (24r)
ams – earth (land?); *terre* B (25r)
anesjouan – heart; *le cœur* B (24v)
Anotman – Carissos of the mission at Camargo; *Carissos de la mission de Camargo* B (26r)³
antajo – stars; *étoiles* B (24v)
aoû – louse; *pou* B (24r)
aouaie – rain; *pluie; eau (pluie)* B (25v, 24v)
aoue – hill; *une colline* B (25v)
aoues – cold; *frais* B (25v) – see also **äwéss, häwéss**
apar – stone; *pierre* B (25r)
apejan – neck; *col* B (25r)

³ For a description of the indigenous people of the mission at Camargo see Berlandier (1980:430).

aque – beard; *barbe* B (25r)
aranguá – see **χáíma aranguá**
aranguás – see **χáíma aranguás**
aricoua – eyes; *yeux* B (25r)
arókwan – eye; *ojo* S (40)
aséχuka – tail; *cola* S (62) – see also **ásuχuga**
âsia – falcon; *faucon (gavillan)* B (24r)
ásuχuga – tail (of a dog); *cola (del perro)* S (55) – see also **aséχuka**
at-chemena-oua – fingernails; *les ongles* B (24v)
átsiu – to grab (to give?); *agarrar (dar?)* S (62)
aura – yellow; *jaune* B (25v)
äwéss, häwéss – cold; *el frio* S (56) – see also **aoues**
awóyo – go there! let’s go!; *va allá! vámonos!* S (57)⁴
ayésema – foot, *el pié* S (41)
ayésim – foot, *pié* S (57)
baí, bá-i – black, dark; night; *negro, prieto; noche* S (41, 55)
bra-ia – black; *noir* B (25v)
cabouia – firestone; *pierre à feu* B (25r)
cajoua-a – belly; *le ventre* B (24v) – see also **kóχ**
cama – cat; *chat domestique* B (24v) – see also **kaman**
camācoua – hair; *cheveux* B (25r)
campūa – shoes; *souliers* B (25v)
caneam – breasts; *les seins* B (24v) – see also **knám, kěnáam**
caoujama – shield; *chimal ou bouclier* B (25r)
capa – night; *la nuit* B (26r)
capi-aou – flea; *puce* B (24r)
chémasetta – ant; *fourmi* B (24r)
choua-ou – tobacco; *tabac* B – see also **su-á-u; suá-u**
chouare – moon; *lune* B (24v)
coua adelma – saddle; *une selle* B (25v)
couaiajamea – knife; *couteau* B (25r) – see also **guayá’h**
coua-iam – dance; *le fandango* B (25v)
couatasa – priest; *un prêtre* B (25v)
couatasa-uma – church; *une église* B (25v)
couba-ajâ – lion; *lion* B (24r)
coue-aoue-jajan – married woman; *femme mariée* B (24v)
cuau – dog; *chien* B (24r)
cucattera – horse; *cheval* B (24r) – see also **kokátere**
dá-än – salt; *la sal* S (55)
dán – mesquite leaf; *hoja de mesquite* S (40) – see also **tánie**
dapouj – stick; *baton (palo)* B (25r)
dópax – stick, tree; *palo, árbol* S (41)
ěhiá-u – knife or sword; *belduque* S (40)

⁴ ‘va allá!’, thus in Gatschet’s manuscript. The exclamation mark suggests an imperative was intended but *va* is third person singular indicative. The word *vámonos* is first written ‘vamos nos’ and then the ‘s’ at the end of the first word is struck out.

- esmók** – hog; *cochino / marano; marano (hog)* S (41)
éta⁵ – down; *para abajo* S (54)
gamáro – hare; *la liebre* S (55)
gapáχ – turtle; *tortuga* S (40)
gapáhia – turtle; *tortuga* M (40)
garópa – hat; *sombrero* S (54)
guayá'h – knife or sword; *belduque* M (40) – see also **couaiajamea**
gurám, gŭrám – wind or air; *viento o el aire* S (54) – see also **ouraman**
χaguátema – loincloth; *pavico, raguero*⁶ S (62)
χaxáme – to eat, for eating, food; *para comer, comida* S (41)
haháme kēmás – to eat meat; *comer carne* S (57)
χαίμα – Indian; *un Indio* S (41) – see also **katám χαίμα**
χαίμα aranguá – local Indian, Comecrudo Indian; *Indio Comecrudo, Indio de por aquí* S (41)
χαίμα aranguás – Tampacuás Indian; *un I. Tampacuás* S (54)
χákue – weep (he is weeping); *está llorando* S (56)
hāwáss – blanket, poncho; *fresada*,⁷ *American blanket* S (56)
hāwéss – see **āwéss, hāwéss**
hayámta⁸ – north; *el norte; norte* S (54, 57)
χuáχe, χuáχe – for drinking, drinks (water?); *para beber, bebidas* S (41)
χuáχe χuánpa – low or distant water (low tide? half-empty cup?); *está bajo, agua que se retira* S (62)
huáhhe – boy (?); *pañó chiquito (nursing)*⁹ (S, 57) – see also **huwáχe** and **χuwáχi**
huá'hle – (he) nurses; *mama (él)* S (57)
χuináχe – man; *hombre* S (40)
(h)uánpa, χuánpa – far, distant; *lejos* S (41) – see also **χuáχe χuánpa**
huwáχe – boy; *chiquito (man)* S (40) – see also **huáhhe** and **χuwáχi**
χuwáχi – boy; *el niño* S (56) – see also **huáhhe** and **huwáχe**
iae – nose; *nez* B (25r)
icapae – daughter; *fille* B (26r)
ichan – son; *fils* B (26r)
ionapua – son-in-law; *gendre* B (26r)
iquae-aouem an – husband; *mari* B (26r)
ja-e – hand; *la main* B (24v)
jaiama – winter; *hiver* B (26r)
kai-ana-ka-coua – eggs; *oeufs* B (24v)
kajuan – hide of bison; *peau de bison* B (24r)
kám – bed; *cama* S (54)
káma – to wake up (?); *amanecer* S (62)

⁵ Confusion surrounds the Cotoname words for the directions, consult pages 54 and 57 of Gatschet's field notes.

⁶ It would seem that *raguero* is an error for *braguero*. We are grateful to Wikipedia contributor Amble for suggesting this.

⁷ Standard Spanish *frazada*.

⁸ Confusion surrounds the Cotoname words for the directions, consult pages 54 and 57 of Gatschet's field notes.

⁹ Nursing male infant held in a shawl?

- kaman** – cat; *chat des bois* B (24r) – see also **cama**
kamaplaí – tortilla; *tortilla* S (41)
kaoua – arrow; *flèche* B (25r) – see also **ká-u, kaú**
kápěra – goat; *la cabra* S (40)
kápia – skunk pig; *javalin* M (40)
kápio – skunk pig; *javalin* S (40)
kapitán – chief; *jefe Indio* S (62)
kápřa – stars; *las estrellas* S (40)
karakór – crane; *la grulla, crane* S (56)
katám – big; *grande* S (41)
katám – woman; *mujer* S (40) – see also **katema**
katám χaíma – Indian woman; *una India* S (41) – see also **χaíma**
kátāra – big, tall; *grande, alto* S (62)
katema – woman; *une femme* B (25r) – see also **katám**
katema-jo – girl; *petite fille* B (25r)
katówan – right arm; *brazo derecho* S (62)
ká-u, kaú – cane, reed, arrow; *caña, carrizo; flecha* S (41, 62) – see also **kaoua**
keafuea – man, *un hombre* B (25r)
keaoua – snake; *serpent à sonnette* B (24r) – see also **kiá-uχa, kiaúχa**
Keiajamte – Cottonames; *Cotonames* B (26r)
kei-oua – testicles; *les testicules* B (24v)
kem – bow; *arc* B (25r)
kemaa – sky; *ciel* B (24v)
kemas – (large) deer; *chevreuil grand* B (24r)
kěmás, kemás – deer, meat; *venado; carne* S (40, 41) – see also **haháme kěmás**
kemása, kemásia – deer; *venado* M (40)
kemás nán – female deer; *venado hembra* S (40) – see also **nán**
kemas-pauâ – small deer; *chevreuil petit* B (24r)
kěmás yómo – male deer; *venado macho* S (40) – see also **yómo**
kemma – bow; *el arco* S (62)
kěnám – see **knám, kěnám**
kěnáχ – (it is) good; *está bueno* S (62) – see also **sá kěnaχ**
kěwáwia – dog; *perro* M (40) – see also **cuau** and **ko wá-u**
kiá’hem – rabbit; *el conejo* S (55)
kiá-uχa, kiaúχa – snakes; *víboras* S (54) – see also **keaoua**
kissá – vixen; *la zorra* S (55)
knám, kěnám – breast, milk; *la chiche (also milk)* S (57) – see also **caneam**
ko wá-u – dog; *perro* S (40) – see also **cuau** and **kěwáwia**
koai – feather; *pluma (de pájaros)* S (56) – see also **kuwai, kuai**
kokátere – horse; *caballo* M, S (40) – see also **cucattera**
kombóχ – wolf; *el lobo* S (55)
komióm – bird; *pájaro* S (56)
komióp – gun, iron; *fusil; fierro (hierro, Span.)* S (55, 56)
komiópo – knife; *navaja* S (54)
komoí – metate (mealing stone); *el metate* S (41)
koua-sam – boy; *garçon* B (25r)
kóχ – belly; *panza, vientre* S (62) – see also **cajoua-a**

- koyáma** – sing; *cantar* S (55) – see also **okáwe koyáma** and **coua-iam**
krák – goose (?); *ánsere*¹⁰ S (56)
kúan – spider; *araignée* B (24r)
kuwaí, kuaí – feather; *la pluma* S (55) – see also **koai**
kuwéle – guts; *tripas, adentro* S (62)
kuwósam – boy; *muchachito; chiquito* S (40, 41)
kuwósom – girl; *muchachita* S (40)
ma-coua – head; *tête* B (25r)
makuát – head, face, body, hair; *cabeza; cara, cuerpo; pelo* S (40, 54)
mán – fire; *fire, lumbre* M (40)
mané – fire; *feu* B (25r)
máně'h – fire; *fire, lumbre* S (40)
ma-oua – heat; *chaleur* B (25v)
mátsěkuka – (he) sleeps; *duerme* S (41)
máyen – foggy; *nieblinazo*¹¹ S (56)
mcoua-amcha – gun; *fusil* B (25r)
mda-je – smoke; *fumée* B (25v)
Meacknan – Garza people; *Garzas* B (26r) – see also **Miákan**
mecou-aampscha – powder; *poudre* B (25r)
mesó-i – white; *blanco* S (41)
miaan – turkey; *dinde* B (24r)
Miákan – Indians at Mier;¹² *Mier; the Indians there were; (idioma non Comecrudo non Cotonamo)* S (54) – see also **Meacknan**
miápa – wings; *las alas* S (55)
msa-a – red; *rouge* B (25v)
msá-ě – red; *colorado* S (55)
mtára – for running, to run (?); *para correr* S (41)
mtapera – lightning; *éclair* B (24v)
nai – frog; *grenouille* B (24r)
nán – female; *hembra* S (40) – see also **kemás nán** and **oiaiou-nan**
náxe – chair, seat; *silla, asiento* S (57)
ó, ó; õ – sun, day; *sol; día* S (40, 55) – see also **aaú**
oiaiou-nan – cow; *vache* B (24r) – see also **nán**
okáwe koyáma – he is going to dance; *va a bailar* S (55) – see also **koyáma**
otá-uma¹³ – up (?); *para arriba* S (54)
otá-ume¹⁴ – east; *oriente!* S (57)
ouamina-joua – summer; *été* B (26r)
oue-uma – ranchería; *une rancherie* B (25v)
ouia-couaoua – young lady; *demoiselle* B (24v)
ouma – house; *maison* B (25v)

¹⁰ Presumably a variant or misspelling of *ánsara*.

¹¹ Presumably a variant or misspelling of *nieblinoso*.

¹² For a description of the Garzas of Mier see Berlandier (1980:428–429).

¹³ Confusion surrounds the Cotoname words for the directions, consult pages 54 and 57 of Gatschet's field notes.

¹⁴ Confusion surrounds the Cotoname words for the directions, consult pages 54 and 57 of Gatschet's field notes.

- oupaja** – cowardly; *lâche* B (25v)
ouraman – wind; *vent* B (25r) – see also **gurám, gŭrám**
ousa-ar – white; *blanc* B (25v)
ov’h, o’χ (curious sound with glottis open) – afternoon; *tarde* S (55)
páma – to shout; *gritar* S (41)
paúne – pipe (for tobacco), smoking; *pipa (a tabaco) y chupar* S (56) – see also **pó-una** and **pó-une**
páwe – for sitting, sit!; *para sentar; asienta te!*¹⁵ S (55, 57)
páwia – to stop(?), to stand (?); *parar* S (55)¹⁶
peen – earth, soil; *terra (sol)* B (24v)
pén – earth, soil; *tierra; lodo* S (40)
pé-na – forest; *une forêt* B (25v)
piajapa – brave; *valiente* B (25v)
pó-una – dust; *polvo de tierra* S (41) – see also **paúne** and **pó-une**
pó-une – to blow; *soplar* S (62) – see also **paúne** and **pó-una**
pra-a – penis; *la verge* B (24v)
qui – niece; *nièce* B (26r)
quia-jan – daughter-in-law; *belle-fille* B (26r)
quima(ma)-(mon) – father; *père* B (26r)
quimea – aunt; *tante* B (26r)
quimpet-sae – brother; *frère* B (26r)
quimp-jro – sister; *sœur* B (26r)
quina – mother; *mère* B (26r)
quiounana – nephew; *neveu* B (26r)
quiquaima – uncle; *oncle* B (26r)
quisotso – father-in-law; *beau-père* B (26r)
quisotsian – mother-in-law; *belle-mère* B (26r)
sá kěnaχ – (it is) not good; *está malo, no está bueno* S (62)
sá’h, sǎx – blood; *sangre* S (54)
sajé – blood; *le sang* B (24v)
sánχe – come here! *vien acá!* S (57)¹⁷
sa-oua – boy; *garçon* B (24v)
sapa – bee; *abeille* B (24r)
sea-a – buttocks; *les fesses* B (24v)
séta¹⁸ – south; *sur; una de ellos; puntos cardinales, also in Comecrudo* S (57, 55)
sevouia – ears; *oreilles* B (25r) – likely wrong¹⁹
séwuya – sheep; *oveja* S (40)
séwuya – goats; *las cabras* M (40)
u machouma-ti – sleep; *le sommeil* B (24v)

¹⁵ Presumably a misspelling of *siéntate*.

¹⁶ The situation is confusing. The word *levántate* is written on the same line but at a substantial distance. Possibly *páwia* is another form of *páwe*.

¹⁷ The exclamation mark suggests an imperative but *viene* is a third person form.

¹⁸ See the introductory paragraph on the confusion surrounding the Cotoname words for the directions.

¹⁹ The Cotoname form *sevouia* is essentially identical to *séwuya*, “sheep”. Along the way there must have been a mix-up between Spanish *ovejas* “sheep” and *orejas* “ears”.

su-á-u; suá-u – tobacco, grass, smoking; *tabaco, yerbas, zacate; tabaco, cigarro; chupar cigarro* S (41, 56, 57) – see also **choua-ou**
tánie – mesquite; *mesquite* M (40) – see also **dán**
tawaló – corn; *maíz* S (40)
tháwě – pinto (beans?); *pinto* S (57)
titcháχ mén? – what do you want? *que quiere Usted?* S (57)
tsēmá'h – mouse; *ratón y ratoncito* S (62)
wáměna – prickly pear; *la tuna* S (40)
wámína – prickly pear; *la tuna* M (40)
wapχáp – corn husk; *paja de maíz* S (57)
wátěχo – die (he died); *se murió* S (41)
wátχuka – to kill; *matar* S (41)
wéfta²⁰ – west (up? east?) *oeste (arriba!); de parte abájo, (este)* S (55, 57)
wiyá-u kátāra – large cow; *la vaca grande* S (56)
wuyopá-u – calf; *becerro chiquito* S (56)
yá'ěχ, yá'h, yá'χ – nose; *nariz* S (57)
yá'h – sweet (to eat); *dulce (de comer)* S (57)
yómo – horn, male; *horn (los cuernos); macho* S (54, 40)

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²⁰ See the introductory paragraph on the confusion surrounding the Cotoname words for the directions.

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British Library add. ms. 38720, f. 24r

Francais	Carisso de Camargo
Bison	
peau de bison	kajuan
abeille	sapa
aigle	
araignée	kûan
chevreuil grand	kemas
ours noir	
chat des bois	kaman
chauve souris	
chien	cuau
poule	
corbeau	
faucon (gavillan)	âsia ? ²¹
fourmi	chémasetta
grenouille	nai
poisson	ám
caiman	
lion	couba-ajâ
dinde	miaan
chevreuil petit	kemas-pauâ
cheval	cucattera
bœuf	
vache	oiaiou-nan ²²
chèvré ²³	
serp ^t a sonnettes ²⁴	keaoua
écureuil ²⁵	
puce	capi-aou
pou	aoû

²¹ Question mark in original.

²² Third letter smudged and ambiguous.

²³ I.e. *chèvre*.

²⁴ I.e. *serpent à sonnette*.

²⁵ I.e. *écureuil*.

British Library add. ms. 38720, f. 24v

Franc.	Carisso de Camargo
cochon	
chat dom ^e ²⁶	cama
soleil	aau ²⁷
lune	chouare
étoiles	antajo
ciel	kemaa
éclair	mtapera
tonnerre	aaqouâ
eau (pluie)	aouaie
terra ²⁸ (sol)	peen
les seins	caneam
le cœur	anesjouan
le ventre	cajoua-a
la matrice	aiam-na
la verge	pra-a
les fesses	sea-a
les testicules	kei-oua ²⁹
les jambes	
le genou	aime-a-cou
le pied	aia-ia
la main	ja-e
les ongles	at-ehemena-oua
demoiselle	ouia-couaoua
garçon	sa-oua
homme marié	aim-jajan
femme mariée	coue-aoue-jajan
le sang	sajé
le sommeil	u machouma-ti
œufs	kai-ana-ka-coua

²⁶ I.e. *chat domestique*.

²⁷ Or possibly aan.

²⁸ The word *terra* could be Latin or an accidental mix of French *terre* and Spanish *tierra*.

²⁹ Or possibly kei-vua.

British Library add. ms. 38720, f. 25r

Franc.	Carisso de Camargo
feu	mané
Pierre	apar
vent	ouraman
terre	ams
agua	aje
fusil	mcoua-amcha ³⁰
flèche ³¹	kaoua
arc	kem
lame	
couteau	couaiajamea
poudre	mecou-aampscha ? ³²
balles	
chimal ou bouclier	caoujama
baton (palo)	dapouj
Pierre à feu	cabouia
un homme	keafuea ³³
une femme	katema
petit garçon ³⁴	koua-sam
pe ^{te} fille	katema-jo
tete ³⁵	ma-coua
yeux	aricoua
bouche	aje-a (sans la langue) ³⁶
nez	iae
oreilles	sevouia
cheveux	camācoua
barbe	aque
dente sup ^{es} ³⁷	aje-ouēma
idem inf	aje-outehen
col	apejan
côtes	ajouan
bras	aje-oura

³⁰ The end of the word is corrected and the final letter is ambiguous.

³¹ I.e. *flèche*.

³² Question mark in original.

³³ The third letter is corrected and unclear. The f is unexpected but it does not seem to be j.

³⁴ I.e. *garçon*.

³⁵ I.e. *tête*.

³⁶ The word *sans* is unclear.

³⁷ I.e. *dents supérieures*. The form *dente* could be a mix of French *dent* and Spanish *diente*.

British Library add. ms. 38720, f. 25v

Français	Carriso de Camargo
doigts	
le pouce	a-eihe-manao
—	—
dieu	Ajehouaan (pron ^z du nez)
un pretre ³⁸	couatasa
une église	couatasa-uma
une croix	
—	—
La mer	Ajuahué
Rio grande	Ajebaham (R. g. ^{de})
Rio de S. Juan	
une foret ³⁹	pé-na
un chemin	
une riviere ⁴⁰	Aje-an
une rancherie	oue-uma
une selle	coua adelma
des étrières	
souliers	campūa ⁴¹
une colline	aoue
une montagne	
valiente	piajapa
lâche	oupaja
blanc	ousa-ar
noir	bra-ia
rouge	msa-a
jaune	aura
vert	
maison	ouma
tabac	choua-ou
pluie	aouaie
chaleur	ma-oua
frais	aoues
fumée	mda-je
le fandango	coua-iam

³⁸ I.e. *prêtre*.

³⁹ I.e. *forêt*.

⁴⁰ I.e. *rivière*.

⁴¹ The letter with the macron is uncertain.

British Library add. ms. 38720, f. 26r

Français	Carriso de Camargo
été ⁴²	ouamina-joua
hiver	jaiama
nord	
sud	
ouest	
est	
le jour	aja
la nuit	capa
un mois	
pere ⁴³	quima(ma)-(mon)
mere ⁴⁴	quina
fil	ichan
fille	icapae
beau pere ⁴⁵	quisotso
belle mere ⁴⁶	quisotsian
gendre	ionapna ⁴⁷
belle-fille	quia-jan
tente ⁴⁸	quimea
oncle	quiquaima
neveu	quiounana
nièce ⁴⁹	qui
mari	iquae-aouem an ⁵⁰
sœur	quimp-jro
frère ⁵¹	quimpet-sae ⁵²

⁴² I.e. *été*.

⁴³ I.e. *père*.

⁴⁴ I.e. *mère*.

⁴⁵ I.e. *beau-père*.

⁴⁶ I.e. *belle-mère*.

⁴⁷ The third letter is smudged and unclear.

⁴⁸ I.e. *tante*.

⁴⁹ I.e. *nièce*.

⁵⁰ Or possibly *iquoe* etc.

⁵¹ The word seems to have been corrected.

⁵² The final 'e' might be a 'c'.

British Library add. ms. 38720, f. 26v

Francais	Carriso de Camargo
Comanche	
Lipan	
Tancahues	
Garzas	Meacknan
Cotonames	Keiajamte
Carisso de Camargo	
Carissos de la mission de Camargo	Anotman

British Library additional ms. 38720

*Vocabulaires de diverses peuplades nomades
des parties septentrionales du Mexique*

Jean Louis Berlandier and Rafael Chowell, ca. 1828–1829

The vocabulary occupies six pages of the manuscript,
from f. 24 recto to f. 26 verso.

Photographs taken by Haukur Þorgeirsson
at the British Library on April 29, 2024.

Vocabulaire des langues de quelques tribus civilisées des forêts du Rio Bravo del Norte

244

français	Carisso de Camargo	Mulato
Bison		
peau de bison	trajuan	Camassamaiva
habille " " " "	sapa	hemiel
angle " " " "		sepiahonec
raigne " " " "	Ruan	iapeteamp.
chevreuil grand " " " "	Remas	ouaou
ours noir " " " "		enhané
chat des bois " " " "	Raman	clampa-taiasuiap.
chame souris " " " "		ouelet.
chien " " " "	cuau	ouisi.
meule " " " "		Plaamp.
corbeau " " " "		Campolamaie.
saumon (gavillan) " " " "	âia ?	Conat.
ourmi " " " "	chémasetta	ahouelet.
grenouille " " " "	nai	Piemett.
poisson " " " "	am	aklaips.
saumon " " " "		atones.
lion " " " "	couba-aja	paouaphipau
oiseau " " " "	miaan	couepet.
chevreuil petit " " " "	Remas-pava	maacuet.
Cheval " " " "	Cucattera	enouehitcha.
sauf " " " "		paouap.
vache " " " "	Neiou-nan	houacete.
chèvre " " " "		Wend paRen?
troupeaux à sonnettes " " " "	Reaoua	Capel.
chevreuil " " " "		ouemse armio.
meule " " " "	capi-aou	Smâs.
meule " " " "	ou	melet.
meule " " " "	ou	ack.

58

Créole de Camargue.

en Malais
emelia bouek.

Malais

le ciel	Camad	
le chat	pan	al
le lait	chouare	escan
la lune	antajo	Petitioni.
les étoiles	Kehaa	apel.
le ciel	antaperad	La.
le tonnerre	aagoua	pamat.
l'eau (pluie)	rouie	aapamesai.
la terre (sol)	peen	camla.
les seins	caniam	don.
le cœur	anesjanan	paia set.
le ventre	cajona-a	onapel.
la matrice	aiam-na	
la verge	ypa-a	
les fosses	sea-a	
les testicules	Kei-vua	
les jambes		
le genou	aine-a-cou	jalel.
le pied	ia-ia	ia po que.
la main	pa-e	hemi.
les ongles	at-chemena-oua	maper.
demoiselle	oua-conaoua	navisee.
garçon	sa-oua	Ken Katmal
homme marié	ain-jajan	baacouel.
femme mariée	coue-houe-jajan	egna.
le sang	saje	Kempacouieou.
le sommeil	umachouma-ti	Piaoit.
oeufs	Kai-ana-Ka-coua	ouapemet.
		Kamiao.

Franc.	Cariso de Camargo.	in Malabo.
mané	mané	leoul.
apar	apar	paion.
buraman	buraman	palet.
ans	ans	apanche.
aje	aje	tainatapel.
meou-amb-choa	meou-amb-choa	taoul.
Keona	Keona	ca.
Rem	Rem	ca.
lonaijama	lonaijama	ca.
meou-ampseba?	meou-ampseba?	ca.
chimal ou bouehir	carujama	ca.
baton (palo)	Dapouj	ca.
Pierre à feu	Carbonia	ca.
un homme	Reafuea	ca.
une femme	Netema	ca.
Petit garçon	Rond-sani	ca.
Pt. fille	Netema-jp	ca.
tete	ma-cota	ca.
yeux	ariona	ca.
bruche	aje-a-justa (langue)	ca.
mes	iac	ca.
oreilles	seviaia	ca.
chevena	camacoua	ca.
barbe	aque	ca.
dente sup.	aje-ouama	ca.
dent inf	aje-ouctehen	ca.
col	apejan	ca.
cotes	ajawan	ca.
bras	aje-oua	ca.

Français.	Carriso de Camargo.	en Melato.
Doigts	a-liche-manav	mapi.
le yonce	Ajehouan (prou ² du nez)	—
un pretre	Conatare	Quemaie
une eglise	Conatare-uma	—
une croix	—	—
La mer	Ajuahe	Atanaie
l'io grande	Ajebaham (M.g. ^{te})	Atnaou
l'io del Juan	—	Atnaou paha
une frot	ye-na	ouial.
un chemin	—	—
une riviere	Aje-an	aal?
une rancherie	One-uma	—
une selle	—	iae.
des etriers	cona adelma	ofaia pacanda
rochers	—	Amalaia.
une colline	campas	—
une montagne	aoue	panestaila
valiente	—	aoui.
l'ache	pijapa	remaia.
l'ane	apaja	maepato-La
soir	oua-ar	sectampe Juan
orange	bra-ia	tepee.
l'ame	msa-a	ouia-to.
l'est	arra	pan-set.
l'urisan	—	paie soy.
tabac	uma	caielait.
l'pluie	chona-ou	ial.
chaleur	ouaie	baa.
l'froid	nea-oua	—
l'fumee	aoues	pasotamba.
le fandango	nda-je	paselliaou.
	oua-ian	caion
	—	ouanpanat.

Carrizo de Camargo.		en Malabo
Quamma-jona	" " " " " "	lamtae
Maiana	" " " " " "	emajae
" " " " " "	" " " " " "	galitias-Popa
" " " " " "	" " " " " "	Komlet.
" " " " " "	" " " " " "	Riam
" " " " " "	" " " " " "	let.
aja	" " " " " "	Semi
capa	" " " " " "	patotian
Pere	quina(maj)-(mon)	iacpakee.
mere	quina	Kemiacpakee.
Fils	ichan	Keela?
Fille	icapae	Keela?
beau pere	quisatto	Keemaan.
belle mere	quisotrian	Kolto.
grandre	ionajina	
belle fille	quia-jan	
tante	quinaea	KeKiam.
Oncle	quiquaina	tetmatavetomat.
neveu	quionnana	Kesat.
nièce	qui	Keelat vetomat.
mari	igual-avemana	KeKouan
jeun	quimp-jra	Kafiquen?
frere	quimpet-sac	Kafse.

B 26v

Français.	Carriso de Camargo.	en Nohato.
Comanche " " "		Sasalcames.
Lipan " " "		Wend.
Tancahués " "		Tancahués.
Garcas " " "	Moacthuán " " "	Atanauajapaca
Cotonames " " "	Reiajante " " "	Onacou ma iend
Carriso de camargo.		Cocuatouand.
Carrissas de la mission de camargo " " "	} " Anotman " " "	Onaspacan.

NAA MS 297-a

Albert S. Gatschet's Cotoname field notes
from his visit to Las Prietas in December 1886.

Pages 40–41, 54–57, 62 contain Cotoname material
and are included here.

Photographs taken by Alaric Hall
at the National Anthropological Archives
on November 14, 2017.

40.

Cotoname:
from miterio; see 54 pp.

~~Art: muchacho, muchacho is hombre mayor~~

- cavallo# kokatere, yes
- las cabras séwuya, (see # 52.) la cabra, kápëra
oveja, Santos
- javalin kápia 17, S. kápia
- perro kewáwia, S. kowa'-u
- operado kemása, kemádia, S. kemás (macho, yómo)
Kemás man hembra
- la tuna wámina (au lumbú) S. wámëna
- mesquite tánie, S. dán; ~~loja~~ de mesquite
- agua á'h S. á'x, áx
- tortuga ~~patahía~~; gapáhía, S. gapáx
Los Tjony nacaban toditos; tambien by Pintus.
- for man; ~~lumbre~~, S. mané'h
- velduque guayaá'h (Tijon # quizzn), S. # éhia'-u
From Santos Cavazos: (Dec. 11, 1886)

- cabeza makuát napab:
- Cara, cuerpo. makuát(?) casa, jacalli.
- ojo ó'xá arókoan sol ó, ó'
- hombre xuaináxe luna
- mayor xatám las estrellas kápia
- muchacho kuwó'sam maiz tawalo'
- muchachita kuwó'som tierra péu
- chiquito (man) # kuwáxe

S 41

La norma - ~~improbable~~; explains miracle & ~~Portuguese~~ ~~Norman~~ 41
 One ~~Two~~ ~~Three~~ ~~Four~~ ~~Five~~ ~~Six~~ ~~Seven~~ ~~Eight~~ ~~Nine~~ ~~Ten~~
~~my~~ ~~two~~ ~~three~~ ~~four~~ ~~five~~ ~~six~~ ~~seven~~ ~~eight~~ ~~nine~~ ~~ten~~ ~~eleven~~ ~~twelve~~ ~~thirteen~~ ~~fourteen~~ ~~fifteen~~ ~~sixteen~~ ~~seventeen~~ ~~eighteen~~ ~~nineteen~~ ~~twenty~~
 Fernando, +, Candido +, dijo ^{de} un de ellos.

mazorca de maiz: tobaco, zacate su-a-u = yerbas.

palto, arbol dopax

arena

la hacha

carrizo ka-u ^{pour couvrir}

rio ax katam (Rio Grande)

caña ka-u ^{ma ji - straw}

el cielo

polvo de tierra po-una.

el pie ayese ma

lejos (Quánpa; xuánpa !)

carne ke mas (= venado)

(1-10 no sabe)

el pan

mano

brazo

tortilla kamapla

cochine marano } esmo'k

el metate komoi

se murio watexo

comida de para comer xaxame

chiquito kuwosam

bebidas de para beber xuaxe

grande katam

para correr mtara

blanco meso-i

duerme matsekuka

negro, pieto bai

matar watxuka

amerillo

gran pam a

un Indio xaima

hablar

una India katam xaima

camino

Indio comecrudo

xaima de straw arangua
 (Indio de por aquí)

54 Coto name,
(all soyas:) Santos Carvajal. (Cont. of 40).

un Indio Pito // un J. Tampacuás : yaima Aranguás
se hay algunos habl. de idioma:

un Indio Camo Chiquitas. (se acabaron)

Tejones y Indios Castujano (eran a las Pretas);
acabaron

Las Cuevas

Matamoros

Reinosa

Camargo

Mier ; the Indians there were Miakan, idioma

no construido, nor Cotonamo. Mission
de la Bonafes allá - 3 o 5 leguas -
cama : kam

una degato

goru (los cuernos) yomo (of macho) pelo - makuat

navaja komiope.

carva, esqui fe

Sangre sä'h sä'x

sombrero ~~komiope~~ (?) garopa

vestido

Zapatos.

vibras kiauça, kia'-uxa.

bravo, valiente

viento gurám, gurám = 's l'aire.

chubasco

falu (por abajo) eta (sur) por arriba jota-uma
el norte ~~homo~~ hayimta (west)
(then 3 or 4 certain).

Coto Maru

55

una de ellos ^{puntas cardinales} seta (?) (alm. Comencudo)

de parte ^{abajo} wífta (este).

lodo (Wade, Koff) pen - ?

fuera komióp (samus Comencudo)

la sal dá-án

la pluma kuwái, kuái

las alas miápa. (mapí ~~hwa~~ / ~~hwa~~ / ~~hwa~~ - Comenc.)

cola (del perro) deupaga

la libre gamáro

el conejo kiá'hem

el lobo kombóx

la zorra kissá

gorrillo

ardilla

cantar koyáma va bailar okáwe koyáma

chile

colorado msá-é

asiento páwe para sentar

levantate parar páwia

noche bai, bá-i día o; mididía

mañana tarde ov'h, o'x (curios form) wífta (plata o/sun)

S 56

56. Cotoname
 fresca hãwãss (American blanket)
 el frío ãwess, hãwess pájoo komiõm
 el calor

~~vacca~~ wuyopã-u: becerro chiquito
 la vaca ^{grande} wiyã-u kãtãra ~~ca~~ cf. cavallo
 la vela (Rulb)

la gruya karakõr (crane)
 ãwẽre krãk pluma koac' (de pajaro)
 gaviãn

estã llorando xãkue el niño xuwãxi
 mosca akwanãmie (esta mascando)^{ti}

tobaco, cigar su-ã-u
 pipa (ãtãc) paũna e y chupar,
 fierro (hierro, span.) komiõp

~~este~~ moblinazo mãyen

Fampacuã. San Juana; vive en la Volca;
 dos mujeres ^{grandes} Mãtra, Carmelita; e son de Re-
 nosa a Pavãch Pavãjo; en la orilla
 del Rio Grande; ^{-da Espinada} ^{1/2 leguas} ^{cerca} y aguas,
 Shikapi a 30 leguas Sur de Renosa.

Cotoacau

57

Los Gatos; por acá de Monterrey; ore bayun.

(quayacan re ashrub, wata tree (grassy))

nari ya'e'x, ya'x, ya'h

cacheton, cachete gordo: kátara grande (cara)

chupar cigarro suá-u

la chiche (wote. Briff) knám, ké nám, also milk,

máma (el) huá'hle

pie' ayésim

paño choquito huá'hle (wote. Briff).

que quiere Usted? titcháx men?

{ vien ~~pra~~ pronto! sanxe! vien acá!
che venga pronto!

marano semó'k (hog).

dulce (de comer) ya'h

himiána tsáyo (he not understand it)

[Aranaam. kn deeply & please mind to see if it is intelligible to you. Am. (Aranaama informant, J. J.)]

paja de mais wápxáp

comer ~~forte~~ ^{carpe} habáme ké máis

pinto tháwéé Wio Rito (vrsabe)

va allá! vamos nos! awóyo!

asiento te! páwe páwe! sille, asiento, náxe

otá-ume oriente! hayámta! noste,

seta sur wéfta oeste (arriba!)

S 62

62.

Cotoname

cola asixuka panza, vientre koxtripas, adentro kuwélepavico, raquero xaguátemaesta bueno kënáxgrande, alto katáraesta malo, no esta bueno sá kënáxesta bajo

xuáxe

~~agua~~ ~~bajita~~amanecerxuánpa (que ^{apna} se retira)

káma.

arco kémmaflecha

kauí

brazo derecho

katówan

(cf. katawan ~~chif~~, Carr.)soplar pó-une.raton

témá'h

y ratoncito

átziu(¿dar)agarrarjefe ndó

kapitan.

NAA MS 297-b

Albert S. Gatschet's Cotoname vocabulary.

Pages 184–190 contain Cotoname material and are included here.

Photographs taken by Alaric Hall
at the National Anthropological Archives
on November 14, 2017.

184

Cotoname,

a dialect related to Comecrudo; obtained
from Santos Cavazos, Las Prietas, Tamaulipas.

Dec. 11, 1886 & seq. Pag. 40:41. 54-57. 62.

41 áx, áx' agua
áx katám no; Rio Grande

41.54. Aranguá; xáima aranguá(s) Indio de por aquí; this is
a reminiscence of the Karankawa Indians at La
Mesa, Wresteria & partly at Tampacuá's. Some say the
language still.

55.62 áxuxuga cola (del puro &c); aséxuka

57.41 ayésim pie; ayésima
awdyo va allá! vamos!

62. átsiu agarrar; dar?

56. akwanámie está masticando

40. aro'kwan ojo

41. 55. baí, bá-i oscuro, negro, pieto; roche

40. dán mesquite; hoja de mesquite; Com. tán.

55. dá-än la sal

41. dópax palo, arbol

54. éta por abajo (?) seta?

57. 41. esmók marano (hog)

40. ehia'-u velduque

55. gamáro la liebre

40. gapáx tortuga

54. guram virato; aire

54. garópa sombro

hu

huá'hhe mama; máma el;

40. huwáxe chiquito; ^{huwáx'i} huá'hhe peño chiquito, hokwáx.

57. haháme kemas comer carne; same as xaxáme, q.v.

54. 57. hayámta el norte

háwáss fresada, American Flank

háwéss, áwés el frío.

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57. ya'-éx, ya'x, ya'h neriz
 57. ya'h dulce
 54. yómo cuerno (de los machos)

56. karakór gruya
 62. káma amenecer
 62. kapitán jefe Indiv.

56. 57. kátara grande; wiya'-u k. vaca grande
 62. katówan (brazo) derecho
 54. kám cama
 41. ká-w (1) carrizo, for roofing. (2) flecha, kaw.
 41. kamaplaí tortilla
 40. kápéra la cabra, chèvre; las cabrillas
 46. kápío javalin
 40. katám grande; mujer

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62. kēnax' está bueno
62. kēm̄ma' arco (por tirar)
56. kēm̄as' venado carne
57. kenām¹³, knām' tetas; la chiche leche.
54. kiá'-uxa víbora, kiá'uxa.
55. kiá'hhem' el conejo
55. ki'ssá' la zorra
55. kombōx' el lobo
55. koyáma' cantar; okáwe k. va bailar.
56. komiōm' pájaro
- 56.55. koai' pluma (de pájaro); kawai', kuai'
- 56.54.55. komiōp' ferro; komiōpo' navaja
futil.
62. kōx' pansa, vientre
40. kokátere' cavallo
41. komoi' metate
56. krak' ansere
40. kuwá-u, kowá-u ferro
40. kuwō'sam' chiquito; muchachito, muchachita.
kuwai'; see koai'
62. kuwē'le' trapas, adentro

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62. xaguátema parico, raguero
54. 41. xáima Indio; katám x. una India.
41. xaxáme comida y para comer; see laháme.
xákue está llorando;
41. xuáxe bebidas y para beber
62. xuáxe está bajo (lagua en el mar xi).
41. xuánpa, huánpa lejos
xuaináxe hombre.
41. mesó-i blanco
56. máyen nooblnago
54. Miakan xáima, (at Miri)
40. 54. makuát cabeza; cara? pelo!
máne'h lumbre; fre
41. mátsékuka duerme men llote, 57.
miápa. alas; cf. mapí paad, Comer.
41. imtára para correr
55. msá-e colorado

57. na^xe silla, asiento

55. okáwe bañar

57. 54. otá-ume oriente ; por abajo?

ov'h, o'x' tarde (curious sound with letters open)

40. o, o' día ; sol.

41. páma gritar

pá-una pipa ; chupar, pañore sb.; see pó-une

55. páwe asienta te ; para sentar.

55. páwia parar

40. péñ tierra

41. pó-una polvo de tierra.

62. pó-une soplar

62. sa' no ; sa' kénax no está bueno

54. sá'h, sá'x' sangre.

57. sánxe ! ¡ven acá!

57. sêta el sur

40. séwuya oreja

57. 56. 41. su-áw tabaco ; chupar tabaco. ; zacate, yerba

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40. tawalo' maiz; Com. same

57. titchax men? que quiere Usted?

62. tsemá'h raton; ratoncito

wa

40. wámēna la tuna

57. wapxáp paja de maiz

41. wátexo se murió. wátxuka matar.

57. wēfte oeste; arriba

56. wiyd'-u vaca

56. wuyopá'-u beceros chiquito.